

Existence of an Inhibitor of Iodination Reaction in Sheep Submaxillary Extract

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THE presence of iodinating enzyme(s) has been reported in some extrathyroidal tissues¹⁻³. A KI-stimulated peroxidase has been partially purified from goat submaxillary gland and the preparation, although not homogeneous, exhibits both iodinase and peroxidase activities⁴. Recently, it has been shown from our laboratory that thyroxine regulates the iodinase and peroxidase activities of submaxillary gland⁵. Sheep and goat being similar species, we became interested to study the iodinating enzyme of sheep submaxillary gland. Surprisingly, it was observed that extracts of sheep submaxillary gland were unable to catalyse the formation of iodo-tyrosine and did not exhibit any peroxidase activity. All attempts to extract the iodinating enzyme (s) from sheep submaxillary gland including hypo- and hypertonic extraction with KCl, proteolytic digestion of crude extract, etc., failed. Thus, it was assumed that either the sheep submaxillary gland extract contains no iodinating enzyme or that an inhibitor of iodination reaction is present in it. The communication describes the presence of an inhibitor of iodination reaction in the sheep submaxillary gland.

Experimental

Fresh goat and sheep submaxillary glands were collected at the local slaughter house, cooled on ice and stored in deep-freeze. Most of the biochemicals, used in this study, were purchased from Sigma Chemical Company. The iodinating enzyme was assayed by the method of Alexander and Corcoran⁶. The reaction mixture contained, in a final volume of 3.0 ml, 200 μ moles of sodium phosphate buffer of pH 7.0, 0.6 μ mole of mono-iodotyrosine (MIT), 0.1 μ mole of KI and 20 μ Ci of Na¹³¹I (carrier free), 0.5 μ mole of H₂O₂ and a suitable volume of the enzyme preparation. The reaction was started by the addition of H₂O₂ and stopped by the addition 0.2 ml of 0.01 M sodium thiosulphate after incubation for 20 minutes at 37°. 0.6 ml of 50% CCl₄ COOH was added and the solution kept in a boiling water bath for 3 minutes, cooled, and centrifuged at 10,000 \times g for 10 minutes. 2.0 ml aliquots of the deproteinized reaction mixture were transferred immediately to a Dowex 50 W \times 8 (H⁺ form) column (0.8 \times 6 cm) to determine the amount of formation of organically bound iodine as described earlier⁴. The amount of diiodotyrosine (DIT) formation was determined as described by Hati & Datta⁷. The peroxidase activity was measured according to the method of Yip⁸. Protein was estimated by the method of Lowry *et al*⁹ using crystalline bovine serum albumin as standard.

All steps of enzyme preparation was carried out at 4°. A 10% homogenate of submaxillary gland was prepared with 1.16% KCl and centrifuged

at 700 \times g in a Sorvall RC-2B refrigerated superspeed centrifuge for 15 minutes to remove cell debris and nuclei. The supernatant was used as enzyme preparation. All comparisons were made by performing parallel experiments with goat and sheep submaxillary glands under identical conditions.

Results and Discussion

The sheep submaxillary extract (SSE) showed neither iodinase nor peroxidase activity when

Fig. 1. Autoradiogram of the products of the reaction. A and B represent radioactive products obtained after incubation in the presence of goat and sheep submaxillary extracts respectively.

homogenized in 1.16% KCl or 0.25 M Sucrose or 0.05 M Tris-HCl buffer pH 7.6. On the contrary, the goat submaxillary preparation catalysed the iodination of MIT very efficiently under identical conditions (Table 1). Fig 1. describes the formation

TABLE 1—IODINATION OF MIT BY GOAT OR SHEEP SUBMAXILIARY GLAND EXTRACT

System	I ⁻ incorporated (n moles/min/mg. protein)
Goat (0.20 mg)	21.13
Sheep (0.22 mg)	0.18
Sheep (0.44 mg)	0.22

700×g supernatant of both goat and sheep submaxillary extracts were used in this experiment.

of DIT from MIT when the goat enzyme preparation was used. In contrast, using the sheep preparation no DIT formation could be detected. It was naturally thought that this lack of activities in SSE might be due to the absence of these enzymes or if these enzymes are present they remain in an inactive form by the presence of an inhibitor. In order to check whether our extraction procedure was efficient, the sheep submaxillary gland was extracted with various buffers of various pH and the extracts were treated separately with protease, trypsin, chymotrypsin, trypsin plus chymotrypsin and mild heat treatment to get the enzyme released. None of these treatments however indicated the presence of iodinase or peroxidase activities in sheep submaxillary extracts (unpublished data).

To check whether SSE contains any inhibitor of iodinase or peroxidase, iodination reaction was carried out by adding SSE to goat enzyme preparation. Table 2 shows that SSE inhibited

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SHEEP SUBMAXILIARY EXTRACT ON THE IODINATING ACTIVITY OF GOAT SUBMAXILIARY EXTRACT

System	I ⁻ incorporated (n moles/min/mg protein)
Goat (0.21 mg)	21.0
Goat (0.21 mg) + SSE (0.22 mg)	12.1
Goat (0.21 mg) + albumin (0.20 mg)	22.0

In this experiment 105,000×g supernatant of both SSE and goat enzyme preparation were used as bulk of the enzyme as well as the inhibitor are present in the soluble supernatant.

the iodination of MIT catalysed by goat enzyme. The possibility that the inhibitory action of SSE might be due to a competition between iodination of MIT and the protein of SSE as protein can be iodinated. This possibility is ruled out when addition of equal amounts of albumin failed to produce any inhibition of MIT iodination (Table 2).

Addition of increasing concentrations of SSE to the goat enzyme preparation produced a progressive inhibition of MIT iodination whereas it had little effect on peroxidase activity of goat enzyme. Non-dialysability, thermolability and loss of inhibitory

activity on protease treatment indicate that the inhibitor is protein in nature. None of the substrates of iodide peroxidase like MIT, KI and H₂O₂ competes with the inhibitor (Results of these experiments will be published elsewhere). However, the final proof depends on the isolation of the inhibitor in pure form. Attempts are in progress to isolate, purify and study the mode of action of this inhibitor. Although some antithyroid agents are known to inhibit the iodination reaction but no one has yet demonstrated the presence of a naturally occurring protein inhibitor which inhibits significantly the iodination reaction.

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Effect of Temperature on Non-Faradaic Electrolysis

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ONE of the authors has reported^{1,2} that electrolysis of water or dilute alkali metal sulphate solution (~N/1000) at low current density (at or below 5mA/cm²) with platinum electrodes show in general three anomalies, viz.

(1) Volume deficit, (2) Ratio Anomaly, (3) Co-liberation.

These anomalies have been lately confirmed by Gosnell and Venugopalan³ and discussed by others³. Such an electrolytic process has been referred to as non-Faradaic electrolysis (nFE). All previous work was done at room temperature and we have meanwhile found that temperature has a marked influence on the characteristics of nFE. Herein we present a preliminary report of the same.

Effect of Temperature

The main features of the effect of temperature on